

CFD-based ejector design to extend the operating range of ammonia/water absorption heat transformers

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Abstract

The early onset of cut-off conditions, referred to as operational limits, is one of the key factors hindering the adoption of ammonia/water absorption heat transformers (AHTs) in hot climates, particularly during peak summer periods. The relatively low cut-off temperature (30–35°C) arises from the coupling between the generator pressure and the pressure established at the condenser. At high ambient temperatures, condenser pressure increases, which limits the amount of ammonia that can be desorbed in the generator.

One strategy to address this issue is to decouple the condenser and generator pressures, creating a system with three distinct pressure levels. A gas compressor could be used for this purpose; however, this solution is costly and may not be justified, as its operation would be limited to periods of high ambient temperatures. As a simpler alternative, gas ejectors can be employed. To operate the ejector, a portion of the evaporated ammonia is diverted from the evaporator outlet and used to entrain and compress the low-pressure vapor from the desorber, raising it to condenser pressure.

This paper presents the methodology used to design and simulate an ejector integrated into an ammonia/water AHT system. A CFD-based optimization loop was developed to refine the geometry of the mixing chamber. This optimization framework is coupled with high-fidelity 2D CFD simulations that allow for a more reliable design process.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, increasingly complex absorption-cycle architectures –including those incorporating vapor ejectors– have been investigated to enhance cycle performance [1]. Vapor ejectors demonstrates the ability to expand the heat-source operating range of absorption cycles, enabling a COP close to 1 for the H₂O/LiBr single-effect cycle [2] at a heat-source temperature of 200 °C (approximately 80 °C above the conventional range). Similar improvements have been reported for the H₂O/LiBr double-effect cycle [3], achieving a COP around 0.9 at heat-source temperatures between 120 °C and 140 °C (around 20 °C below the typical range). These advancements for H₂O/LiBr systems have subsequently motivated studies on NH₃/H₂O machines [4], which indicate the potential for performance enhancement at higher heat-source temperatures, although further experimental validation is still needed.

Over the past few decades, the rise of CFD-based numerical modeling has undoubtedly extended into the study of ejectors. Previous work [5,6] has demonstrated not only good accuracy in predicting the ejector entrainment ratio (ER) but also strong agreement with local-scale characteristics, such as pressure profiles.

In the framework of the ZIMBA project, an innovative ammonia/water AHT system aiming to produce 15 kW_{th} at 110°C will be developed. It is improved by the integration of a two-phase ejector, designed to stabilize its performance and widen the operating conditions range – in particular under hot conditions.

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The schematic diagram representing the ejector integration in the ZIMBA AHT system (project: <https://zimba-project.eu>) is shown in Figure 1, more information on the detailed architecture can be found in [7].

Figure 1. Scheme of the ZIMBA absorption heat transformer enhanced by the ejector.

This paper focuses on the design and simulation of the ejector via CFD models. An optimization loop allows refining the geometry of the mixing chamber. Since the refrigerant vapor flowing through the ejector has an ammonia concentration close to 1, high-fidelity 2D-CFD simulations incorporating the thermodynamic behavior of pure ammonia are performed, to improve calculation accuracy and to strengthen the design process.

2. Methodology and Materials

In this section, the step-by-step procedure for the ejector design will be described. It is a CFD based design procedure, which can be decomposed into 4 different tackling points. Firstly, defining the target for optimization, following with determining the ejectors geometrical parameters to optimize, then choosing the adequate CFD model, and finally choose the optimization algorithm.

2.1. Defining the target

As the ejector operating conditions – temperature and pressure of the inlets and outlet – are given, the target of the present study is to optimize the **entrainment ratio** (i.e., the ejector efficiency). The ER is defined as the suction mass flow rate divided by the primary mass flow rate. A higher entrainment ratio means that less vapor is required for compression, enabling more vapor for heat production, and a higher COP.

2.2. Defining the ejectors geometrical parameters for optimization

In the AHT system, the split ratio is defined as the fraction of high-pressure ammonia vapor diverted from the evaporator toward the ejector divided by the total flow rate. Its optimal value represents a trade-off: the more the flow rate diverted to the ejector, the higher the condenser pressure reached by the AHT. This allows extending the operating limits beyond the cut-off, which is the goal of the ZIMBA architecture. However, high split ratio implies a lower amount of ammonia vapor reaching the absorber, which directly impacts the useful heat produced by the system. According to simulations by [7], the optimal split is 40%. The thermodynamic properties at the ejector boundaries, simulated with a split ratio of 40%, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Thermodynamic properties at the ejector boundaries with a split ratio of 40%.

	Temperature [°C]	Pressure [bar]	Mass flow rate [kg/h]
Primary flow	106.3	33.5	33.2
Secondary flow	78.3	12.8	46.8
Outlet flow	81.7	14.8	80.0

Knowing the nominal operating conditions, and that the primary flow is choked at the throat ($Mach = 1$), a simple 1D compressible gas theory allows to compute the primary nozzle main sections (inlet, middle, and exit). To avoid recirculation, the diffuser was designed as a truncated cone with a fixed opening angle of 5° . The secondary inlet channel is also fixed, with an angle equal to that of the primary nozzle convergent section.

Figure 2. Sample of a generated mesh representing the vapor flowing in the ejector. The domain is 2D axially symmetric, simulating only half of the ejector 2D section. The mesh is structured multiblock with quadrilateral elements to reduce numerical diffusion, and is refined at walls. In the green box is a zoom of the critical part of the ejector, near the nozzle exit.

This leaves one with 3 parameters heavily influencing the entrainment ratio: **the mixing chamber diameter, the mixing chamber length, and the Nozzle Exit Plane (NXP) distance from the mixing chamber inlet** (Figure 2). The NXP position does not only influence the distance to the mixing chamber, but also the suction area section. As that value decreases, so does the suction area section, which further accelerates the suction flow.

2.3. Defining the CFD model

Simulating the homogeneous condensation inside the ejector is extremely expensive as one simulation can take several hours to reach convergence. This makes the cost of running a parametric optimization prohibitive, and a single-phase approach is adopted.

Furthermore, simulation of a bicomponent fluid remains scarce in literature, and requires an extensive study on this matter in order to properly simulate its physical aspect, along with its undoubtable impact on the condensation process. As a matter of simplification, the fluid is considered pure ammonia in this study.

The setup for the CFD model is presented below:

- 2D axially symmetric domain
- Adiabatic conditions at wall
- Roughness at wall of 50 μm
- Real gas model described via a 3rd order Peng-Robinson equation of state for ammonia
- Reynolds Average turbulence modelling (RANS) with wall function approach
- K- ω SST turbulence model with compressibility effect to correctly reproduce the mixing layer development

The simulations are performed with the software Ansys Fluent v2025.R1 [8]. The single-phase scheme used in the parametric optimization exploits a fully-coupled, implicit, density-based approach, with 2nd order discretization algorithm.

2.4. Defining the optimization model

The optimization procedure chosen is called a “response surface optimization”. The procedure can be divided into 3 main steps. Firstly, it is required to generate a number of initial design points (DP) to feed the surface generator function. The choice of cases should be able to cover a large zone of the design space. Secondly, a response surface is generated based on the given initial cases. It is an analytical function of the ER as a function of the 3 chosen parameters discussed above. Finally, an optimization algorithm explores the surface to look for an optimum.

The sampling-based DOE available in Ansys Design Explorer is used. This type of DOE automatically selects sample points across the design space, ensuring good coverage with a limited number of CFD simulations. Its main advantage is its efficiency in exploring multidimensional design spaces.

The Kriging response surface model is adopted. This type of response surface is well suited for problems with nonlinear behaviors and provides an accurate surrogate model that interpolates the sampled data.

For the optimization, we selected the Nonlinear Programming by Quadratic Lagrangian (NLPQL) algorithm. This gradient-based method is appropriate for single-objective problems with continuous parameters and performs well in finding refined local optima. This matches our case, since the optimization seeks to maximize the ER and the response surface is continuous within the prescribed parameter ranges.

3. Optimization results

3.1. Design process

The flow field within our configuration is analyzed using a fully blind CFD-based optimization algorithm making use of DOE and a response surface. 20 DPs are simulated for the DOE via the in-built sampling procedure [9], and around 100 DPs are needed to reduce the estimated error of the Kriging response surface down to the desired 5% limit. The full optimization procedure – including the DOE phase, the response surface refinement and error testing, and the optimal points validation – took around 180 DPs to produce 3 optimal design candidates. Table 2 compares the initial guessed design with those resulting from the design optimization procedure.

Table 2. Comparison of the different optimal designs produced by the optimization algorithm and the steps of the process. The optimal design is sensitive to changes in mixing chamber radius and length, while it is almost insensitive to changes in the NXP distance.

Case	Mixing chamber length [mm]	Mixing chamber radius [mm]	NXP/mixing chamber distance [mm]	Predicted Entrainment Ratio	Verified Entrainment Ratio
Initial guess	40	2	4	/	1.0355
Optimization starting point	17.5	2	4.5	1.382	1.382
Optimal candidate 1	22.57	2.001	3.26	1.409	1.401
Optimal candidate 2	20.94	1.999	4.67	1.399	1.394
Optimal candidate 3	20.22	1.995	5.07	1.394	1.389

The optimal candidates all possess the same mixing chamber height and their lengths vary by 10% (20 to 22 mm). By contrast, the NXP distance varies by almost 40% between the first candidate and the last. These results suggest that the optimal design is significantly more sensitive to changes in mixing chamber radius and length than to modifications in the NXP distance.

Figure 3 shows a 3D surface of the resulting response surface. This surface is a projection of the full 4D hypersurface, considered for a fixed value of the NXP distance to the mixing chamber, equal to 4.5 mm. The response surface clearly shows the presence of a unique maximum in this projection. This probably means that there is no presence of relative maxima in this ejector design space and the optimal value that we can find by running the optimization algorithm is unique.

Figure 3. Response surface generated by interpolating the calculated design points (grey dots). The response surface models the design space of the ejector, reproducing how the objective function (the ER) varies as a function of the design parameters selected for the optimization (the mixing chamber length and radius).

3.2. Flow field of the resulting geometry

Figure 4 shows the Mach field. The choking occurs near the exit of the nozzle because there is no divergent part. For the same reason, the primary flow at the nozzle exit is under-expanded. This can be noticed by the strong acceleration at the nozzle exit, followed by a sequence of deceleration and expansion inside the mixing chamber.

Figure 4. Mach field inside the ejector's mixing chamber. The white line represents the points with Mach equal to one.

Figure 5 illustrates the contour of the turbulent dissipation rate (ϵ) inside the primary nozzle and mixing chamber. The map shows that turbulence is mostly dissipated inside the mixing layer. This loss is unavoidable, since it originates from the very mechanism that allows the entrainment of the secondary stream. Nevertheless, significant dissipation is also present along the channel walls, though these wall losses cannot be entirely eliminated, they can be mitigated by adopting more aerodynamic wall profiles and by reducing surface roughness.

Figure 5. Turbulent dissipation rate (ϵ) field inside the ejector's primary nozzle and mixing chamber (map in log scale). Turbulence is mostly dissipated inside the mixing layer. However, significant dissipation is present along the channel walls.

4. Conclusion and perspectives

This paper detailed the design methodology of an ejector aimed to be integrated in an ammonia/water AHT. CFD model optimization loop is used to refine the geometry of the mixing chamber. The optimal configuration to reach a targeted entrainment ratio value by running the optimization algorithm appeared to be unique in the allowed range of design parameters. The developed geometry is then used to simulate the behavior of pure ammonia vapor flowing through the ejector. Detailed analysis of the flow field highlights the choking occurrence near the nozzle exit. By providing a map of the turbulent dissipation rate, this initial design simulation gives us insights on the regions of high dissipation and will allow us to introduce several improvements to the geometry, as modifications aimed at creating a more aerodynamic wall profile.

In a second time, simulations with ammonia/water mixture thermodynamic properties, as well as analysis of the impact of the condensation inside the ejector will be considered for further development.

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